

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

FAIR Assessment – LSRI - Conceptual Requirements

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0.2	In progress		Converted to v1.3 template only	Allyson Lister
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Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
GUPRI	Globally unique, persistent and resolvable
GUID	Globally unique and resolvable. Note that often people use this (mistakenly) interchangeably with GUPRI.

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Introduction and Task Management

This document describes a FAIR benchmark and associated components tailored to the needs of the LS-RI cluster within OStrails as part of work package 4. This document is a human-readable, narrative description of this community's requirements for FAIR assessment of databases for any digital object type within the life sciences, without the inclusion of technical details. It follows the [Assess-IF](#) and, once complete, can be used as a starting point for the creation of required technical components.

This document is a work in progress and has been published to show the current state of the benchmark version as per the version listed at the top of this document. Iterative refinement and development will occur and be marked by further versions of this document and associated Assess-IF components.

The following arguments should be passed to this benchmark:

- **Mandatory:** The DOI or URL of the FAIRsharing record for the database being assessed.

This document was created using the v1.3 template found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18244844>. This template can be copied and used within any community to begin preparations for a FAIR benchmark specific to your needs.

FAIR Assessment Conceptual Components - Roadmap		
Task	Status	Notes
1: Benchmark – narrative requirements	Completed	This benchmark evaluates life science databases as there are too many disparate digital object types to capture all.
2: All metrics - narrative requirements	In progress	Mark as complete when all of your metric sections in this document are completed. Iterative refinement may be required before completing step 4.

3: Related standards, databases and collections - registration with FAIRsharing	In progress	Any standards, databases and collections that are required for the correct running of your benchmark should be registered with FAIRsharing and listed in the 'Related Records' area of the metrics sections.
4: Completed first draft of document	In progress	Once all parties are happy with this document, the first draft is complete, and the next task may begin.
5: Benchmark - registration with FAIRsharing	Completed	https://fairsharing.org/7456
6: All metrics - registration with FAIRsharing	In progress	https://fairsharing.org/7455 , https://fairsharing.org/7163 , https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK , https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.NHCOKK

Overview

The Assessment Interoperability Framework (Assess-IF) being used by this community aims to create a uniform approach for defining and running tests (and specifically FAIR tests in the context of this document) by:

1. **Giving the community the power to choose what FAIR means to them:** Until now, using a FAIR tool such as those listed at <https://fairassist.org/tools> meant either selecting from among the benchmarks for FAIR that a given tool provides (which may be unclear or hard to understand exactly what's being tested) or a formal collaboration with tool(s) to ensure they provide a custom FAIR assessment solution for your needs. The Assess-IF allows you to explicitly state how your community defines FAIR, and exactly how it should be tested, measured, weighted and scored.
2. **Encouraging transparency in assessment behaviours:** To date, FAIR assessment has been characterised by disparate behaviours and scores arising from independently authored FAIR Assessment tools, which themselves vary in the level of transparency they exhibit for their tests and benchmarks. The Assess-IF methodology encourages all tools and assessment platforms to register their assessment components (e.g. benchmarks, metrics) in a searchable manner, with rich metadata explaining what is being tested, why, and how. The Assess-IF allows you not only to define FAIR according to your community requirements but also provides a way of making those definitions clear, visible, reusable and extendable. Benchmarks that cannot be discovered via a search, and do not describe themselves sufficiently, do not themselves meet the minimum expectations for FAIRness and make it harder to understand if a particular tool interprets FAIR the way your community requires it to be interpreted.
3. **Defining a consistent report format for assessments:** Because the reports are designed to be understood by any tool, the user can have a wider range of independent tools to select from. Being able to move these reports from one tool to another also allows the user to contextualise their tests, and to explore results from different perspectives.
4. **Enabling Automatic FAIR Testing via APIs:** by creating shared APIs among the different domains (FAIR, SKG, DMP, maDMP) it becomes possible to “embed” assessments into existing tooling. For example, a DMP authoring tool will be able to “call out” to a FAIR Assessment tool to obtain real-time information about the FAIRness of a digital object while the DMP is being written or updated.

Summary of component types

The Assess-IF has seven main “components”, split according to three main categories: **conceptual** components define FAIR for a community in human-readable terms, **software** components provide the actual tests and interpretations of those tests, and **data** components store the results of running an assessment. This template helps you to fully specify the conceptual components for your community definition of FAIR and gives you jumping off points to create the software components and ultimately run assessments to produce data in the form of test results. As such, we have provided a short description of each component so that you can understand the wider framework at a very high level.

The **conceptual components** are:

1. **Dimensions/principles:** Dimensions (for this template, our dimensions are the FAIR Principles) are designed to be subject- and implementation-agnostic criteria or high-level goals that may be refined for particular communities as described in this template. More information on the FAIR principles can be found in the FAIR Principles FAIRsharing record (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.WWI10U>), which provides a wealth of information about them as well as linking to individual records describing all sub-principles.
2. **Benchmarks:** Community-specific groupings of metrics. They provide a narrative describing how a community defines FAIR. Communities can choose the granularity of their benchmarks with regards to subject area and digital object type. Specifically, this means that benchmarks may be agnostic of object type or subject area, or may be scoped as tightly as required by the benchmark authors.
3. **Metrics:** Narrative description that a Test must wholly implement. Each metric should implement exactly one dimension (e.g. one sub-principle from the FAIR Principles). Metrics may be domain-agnostic or not.

A detailed understanding of the remaining components (below) is not required for the purposes of this template, but a short description of each is provided for completeness.

The **software components** are:

1. **Tests:** The instantiation of metrics, executed to assess a digital object in accordance with the metric linked to the test.
2. **Scoring Algorithms:** The instantiation of benchmarks, executed to create community-specific value judgements on the outcomes of tests. They specify the exact set of tests which are to be run by the assessment service together with weightings for each of these tests. Algorithms contextualise the sum of all test results for a given benchmark into a final quantitative assessment result.

The **data components** are:

1. **Test Results:** The output of running a test over a digital object. A test result also contains provenance metadata about the process followed to create it.
2. **Test Result Sets:** A set of test results, together with their respective metadata.
3. **Benchmark Scores:** Obtained after executing a scoring algorithm over a set of test results. The benchmark score includes a value, a log and a link to the test results used to obtain the score.

Types of Metrics

Symbols

- indicate a Generic metric.
- indicates a Specialised metric.
- indicates a section providing more information.

When a community uses this document to describe a benchmark and related metrics, the metrics can be one of two types.

Within OStrails, all principles have corresponding **generic metrics** except for the following: I2, R1.2, R1.3, which communities must **specialise** for their requirements. Such specialised metrics generally need to consider the requirements of both the specific discipline and digital object type being assessed by the benchmark.

Generic Metrics

If a section is labelled **generic**, then all benchmarks should be able to implement the generic metric rather than needing to define a community-specific metric. Generic metrics are those that cover domain-agnostic features, therefore applicable to any discipline, irrespective of the type of digital object being evaluated.

Specialised Metrics

💡 If a section is labelled **specialised**, then the principle is considered highly domain specific, and we suggest that all communities create their own metric to suit their requirements.

Refinements and sufficiency

Small modifications to existing generic metrics may optionally be added as **refinements** to a generic metric within a community document. These are intended to allow communities to specify exactly where a field can be found, e.g. a licence field, within their metadata. These will either be implemented as a specialised test (rather than using the already-created generic test associated with a generic metric) or as a specialised metric. Iterative updates to this document will determine which is appropriate.

While the classification of **generic** and **specialised** metrics is useful and is intended to make it easier to create assessments, there will be circumstances where a given **generic** metric is a *necessary* part of the assessment for a community but is also *insufficient* to wholly describe that community's requirements for that principle.

For example, perhaps a community wishes to specifically check for a particular type of DOI (e.g. one minted by an approved service of their choice) in addition to the presence of any GUPRI type ("any GUPRI" is the definition of the generic F1 GUID metric). In such a case, **refinements** are not appropriate (because the underlying generic metric is *necessary* but not *sufficient*); instead, **specialised** metrics linked to a principle that already has a **generic** metric are appropriate. In this example, the community should use two metrics, both of which are linked to FAIR F1-GUID: one will be the **generic** metric for FAIR F1-GUID and the other will be a new **specialised** metric with the added requirement.

FAIR Assessment of Life Science Repositories and Knowledgebases Benchmark

Benchmark Name and URL	FAIR Assessment of Life Science Repositories and Knowledgebases Benchmark <i>This benchmark, including a complete description, supporting documentation and a full list of associated metrics, can be found at https://fairsharing.org/7456.</i>
Description	The Life Science Repository Benchmark uses FAIRsharing to assess the FAIRness of life science repositories registered there (i.e. repositories and repositories/knowledgebases). It is of primary utility for researchers wishing to choose an appropriate life science repository to submit their data, database managers and the RDM community generally, including any RDM role that requires a high-level evaluation of the alignment of a repository with FAIR. This benchmark coordinates the FAIR assessment of any repository registered in FAIRsharing using metadata stored within the registry. For a repository to be assessed, it only needs to be registered in FAIRsharing. Life science repositories are highly variable and individual datasets from disparate research areas within the life sciences cannot be easily assessed using a single benchmark. Therefore, rather than using a life science dataset as input for this benchmark, the FAIRsharing URL/DOI should be provided. This benchmark will then provide a score for the repository as a higher-level proxy for any content within the repository. Stakeholders wishing a more granular benchmark for more specific life science research areas are invited to create their own benchmarks that complement this one, but which provide more tailored, dataset-specific assessments within those more specific research areas.
Applicability	<i>What digital object(s) will be covered? Object type agnostic</i> <i>What subject area(s) are covered by this benchmark? Life Sciences</i>
Related Resources	This benchmark relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2abjs5
Guidance	More information on this benchmark may be found at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Homepage • Life science databases in FAIRsharing • Scoring Algorithm implementing this benchmark (registered with FAIR Champion)

FAIR Principles F1: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

📄 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a2cea7>.

For our benchmark, this principle is split into its distinct components of the identifiers being 1) GUPRIs, and 2) persistent. These sub-principles are F1-GUID (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>) and F1-PID (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>).

FAIR Principles F1-PID: (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers

💡 We do NOT use the generic metric 'FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Persistence' but instead created a **specialised** metric that parses the FAIRsharing database record metadata and checks that the referenced database mints persistent identifiers.

FAIR Metric - F1-PID - Metadata - Persistent identifiers for database content

Specialised metric name, definition and URL	FAIR Metric - F1-PID - Metadata - Persistent identifiers for database content (FM:F1-PID:M:ARK) https://fairsharing.org/7163 The 'FAIR Metric ARK F1 - Persistent Identifiers for Database Content' is a database-level metric that requires the minting of persistent identifiers for at least some of the content within the database being evaluated. FM ARK F1 expects a FAIRsharing URL or DOI as its input and evaluates that FAIRsharing record for the guaranteed persistence of the identifier schema as defined by the identifier schema record type in FAIRsharing (see our gitbook documentation linked as part of this record for more information about id schemas for databases and how to curate them in a FAIRsharing record). An important facet of FAIR for databases is that they mint persistent identifiers. As described by the GFF, global uniqueness guarantees the unambiguous referencing of the described resource; it is insufficient for it to be unique only locally. Persistence refers to the requirement that this globally unique identifier is never reused elsewhere and continues to identify the same resource over time. These features are key to the Findability of the database being evaluated.	
Related resources	Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2abjs5 	
Guidance	Guidance links <i>(at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance)</i> :	
	URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI
	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/identifier-type	How to link a FAIRsharing database record to the ID schema(s) it implements
	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/registry-type#identifier-schema-records	FAIRsharing identifier schema documentation
	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/globally-unique-persistent-and-resolvable-identifier-schemas	FAIRsharing definition of persistence
	https://www.gofair.foundation/f1	GFF - F1

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URIs	Descriptions
	Negative	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7mm5g5	Indicative negative example (the FAIRsharing record for COD shows that this resource mints its own internal identifiers)
	Positive	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf	Indicative positive example (FAIRsharing record DOI for Zenodo) of identifiers that are also GUPRIs, and therefore persistent as per EOSC-PID-aligned FAIRsharing GUPRI definition.
	Positive	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.fd6003	Indicative positive example (FAIRsharing record DOI for UniProt AC) of identifiers that are persistent but not guaranteed globally unique or resolvable as per EOSC-PID-aligned FAIRsharing GUPRI definition.
Indeterminate	To be added		

FAIR Principles F1-GUID: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

We are using the **generic** metric.

 We are also using a **specialised** metric.

For details of both, please see the subsections below.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness - Gen2-MI-F1A

This is a **generic metric**.

 For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.NHCOKK>.

LS-RI uses the **generic** metric and its associated generic test to check if the identifier being passed to the benchmark is a GUPRI, but this is insufficient for our needs and therefore will only be given a low weighting. More importantly to our benchmark are the type(s) of identifier schemas used by the database referenced in the FAIRsharing record. Therefore, we have also created the **specialised** metric below, which is of primary importance as it will test that the referenced database mints GUPRIs.

Generic metric name and definition

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness - Gen2-MI-F1A

The 'FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness' metric checks whether the identifier schema the provided identifier adheres to is globally unique, persistent and resolvable (a GUPRI); a pass of tests implementing both this and the Gen2-MI-F1B metric will identify a GUPRI as defined by FAIRsharing (see support links in this record for more information). FM Gen2-MI-F1A is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier to be provided and evaluates its identifier schema as a GUPRI. An example implementation would be to use regex matching against registered FAIRsharing identifier schemata and check the global uniqueness, persistence and resolvability fields (see support links in this record for more information). More than one match might signify an issue with the identifier schema matching. If using this example implementation, check the existing identifier schemata in FAIRsharing and please register any that you might need. The uniqueness of an identifier is a necessary condition to unambiguously refer that resource, and that resource alone. Otherwise, an identifier shared by multiple resources will confound efforts to describe that resource, or to use the identifier to retrieve it. For an in-depth understanding of the issues around identifiers, please see <http://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414>.

Links to more information on the generic metric

 For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.NHCOKK>.

 For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>.

FAIR Metric - F1-GUPRI - Metadata - Globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers for database content

💡 We are using a **specialised** metric. '[FAIR Metric ARK F1-GUPRI - Globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers for database content](#)'. This metric parses the FAIRsharing database record metadata and checks that the referenced database mints GUPRIs.

Specialised metric name, definition and URL	<p>FAIR Metric - F1-GUPRI - Metadata - Globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers for database content (FM:F1-GUPRI:M:ARK) https://fairsharing.org/7455</p> <p>The FAIR Metric ARK F1-GUPRI – Globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers for Database Content is a database-level metric that requires the minting of community-relevant, publicly available GUPRIs for at least some of the content within the database being evaluated. FM ARK F1-GUPRI expects a FAIRsharing URL or DOI as its input and evaluates the database described by the FAIRsharing record for the guaranteed global uniqueness, persistence and resolvability of the identifier schema as defined by the identifier schema record type in FAIRsharing (see our gitbook documentation linked as part of this record for more information about id schemas for databases and how to curate them in a FAIRsharing record). As described by the GFF, global uniqueness guarantees the unambiguous referencing of the described resource; it is insufficient for it to be unique only locally. Persistence refers to the requirement that this globally unique identifier is never reused elsewhere and continues to identify the same resource over time. Resolvability of identifier makes it practically useful, with predictable identifier resolution behavior being key (see support links for more information). These features are key to the Findability of the database being evaluated.</p>										
Related resources	<p>Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2abjs5 										
Guidance	<p>Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="311 971 2092 1342"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="318 976 1025 1018">URI</th> <th data-bbox="1037 976 2085 1018">Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="318 1023 1025 1091">https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/identifier-type</td> <td data-bbox="1037 1023 2085 1091">How to link a FAIRsharing database record to the ID schema(s) it implements</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="318 1096 1025 1198">https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/registry-type#identifier-schema-records</td> <td data-bbox="1037 1096 2085 1198">FAIRsharing identifier schema documentation</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="318 1203 1025 1310">https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/globally-unique-persistent-and-resolvable-identifier-schemas</td> <td data-bbox="1037 1203 2085 1310">FAIRsharing definition of global uniqueness, persistence and resolvability</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="318 1315 1025 1342">https://www.gofair.foundation/f1</td> <td data-bbox="1037 1315 2085 1342">GFF - F1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/identifier-type	How to link a FAIRsharing database record to the ID schema(s) it implements	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/registry-type#identifier-schema-records	FAIRsharing identifier schema documentation	https://fairsharing.gitbook.io/fairsharing/record-sections-and-fields/general-information/globally-unique-persistent-and-resolvable-identifier-schemas	FAIRsharing definition of global uniqueness, persistence and resolvability	https://www.gofair.foundation/f1	GFF - F1
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https://www.gofair.foundation/f1	GFF - F1										

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URIs	Descriptions
	Negative	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7mm5g5	Indicative negative example (the FAIRsharing record for COD shows that this resource mints its own internal identifiers)
	Negative	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.fd6003	Indicative negative example (FAIRsharing record DOI for UniProt AC) of identifiers that are persistent but not guaranteed globally unique or resolvable as per EOSC-PID-aligned FAIRsharing GUPRI definition.
	Positive	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf	Indicative positive example (FAIRsharing record DOI for Zenodo) of identifiers that are also GUPRIs as per EOSC-PID-aligned FAIRsharing GUPRI definition.
Indeterminate	To be added		

FAIR-A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

A2 focuses on keeping relevant digital resources available in the future. Data may no longer be accessible either by design (e.g. a defined lifespan within limited financial resources or legal requirements to destroy sensitive data) or by accident. However, given that those data may have been used and are referenced by others, it is important that consumers (including machines) have, at the very least, access to high quality and machine actionable metadata that describes those resources sufficiently to minimally understand their nature and their provenance, even when the relevant data are no longer available. This principle relies heavily on the “second purpose” of principle F3 (the metadata record contains the identifier of the data), because in the case where the data record is no longer available, there must be a clear and precise way of discovering its historical metadata record. This aspect of accessibility is further elaborated in the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7c4d7f>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0c0d21>.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence

☑💡 We use the generic metric [‘FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence’](#) but have written our own **specialised** test. We have done this to ensure that the FAIRsharing metadata for the evaluated database record is always properly checked for a persistence policy. Further information about this test may be found in our [Scoring Algorithm implementing this benchmark \(registered with FAIR Champion\)](#).

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence - Gen2-MI-A2</p> <p><i>This metric checks if there is a policy for metadata persistence. Gen2-MI-A2 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of a persistencePolicy key. Cross-references to data from third-party’s FAIR data and metadata will naturally degrade over time, and become “stale links”. In such cases, it is important for FAIR providers to continue to provide descriptors of what the data was to assist in the continued interpretation of those third-party data. As per FAIR Principle F3, metadata must remain discoverable, even in the absence of the data (and missing data will still be explicit referenced via the data IRI within the metadata). Here are two examples of ways in which this metric might be evaluated. While a test implementation could explore the harvested metadata for something resembling a “persistence policy” property (e.g. http://www.w3.org/2000/10/swap/pim/doc#persistencePolicy), this is often unsuccessful as databases don't always include database-level persistence information at the level of a dataset. To solve this issue, test implementations can use an optional additional argument containing the URL/DOI of the FAIRsharing database record where the digital object is stored, and the FAIRsharing record metadata can be checked for the existence of a persistence policy of the database (see support links for more information). Note that for both methods of checking persistence, the presence of a persistence/preservation policy does not guarantee the quality of that policy; the linked policy may simply state that no preservation will occur.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>🔗 For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK.</p> <p>🔗 For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7c4d7f.</p>